

Barriers in Integrating Traditional and Modern Approaches in Community Health Centers: A Qualitative Study in Gianyar Regency

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Abstract

Integrating complementary traditional medicine with modern medical practices in community health centers (CHCs) presents both opportunities and challenges. In Gianyar Regency, Bali, efforts to promote traditional medicine, such as family medicinal plant programs, have faced significant obstacles. This study aims to explore the feasibility of collaboration among CHC administrators to support such integration. A qualitative study was conducted using eight focus group discussions (FGDs) during mandatory monthly mini-workshops involving all administrators responsible for various CHC programs. These discussions aimed to examine the challenges and potential for integrating traditional and modern medical practices. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes related to barriers and opportunities for collaboration. The findings revealed limited collaboration among administrators due to differing program priorities, professional restrictions preventing doctors from promoting herbal medicine, and financial barriers, including lack of insurance coverage for traditional practices. Other challenges included the greater accessibility and affordability of modern medicine, low community awareness, and inadequate resources. The study suggests that successful integration requires systemic changes, such as revising professional guidelines, expanding insurance coverage, enhancing community education, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. Addressing these barriers is crucial to developing a more holistic and culturally sensitive healthcare system in community settings.

Keywords: traditional medicine integration, community health centers, healthcare collaboration, complementary medicine, health policy barrier

INTRODUCTION

Complementary traditional medicine encompasses a wide range of health practices, knowledge, and beliefs that incorporate plant-based remedies, manual techniques, and spiritual therapies (1–4). These practices have been used for centuries to promote health, prevent disease, and treat various ailments, often in conjunction with cultural and spiritual traditions (5,6). In many communities, especially in regions like Bali, traditional medicine is deeply rooted in local culture and is considered an essential part of holistic well-being (7,8). Complementary traditional medicine, such as herbal treatments, massage therapy, and spiritual healing, often exists alongside modern medical practices in community health settings. As healthcare systems

increasingly seek to provide more comprehensive and culturally sensitive care, integrating traditional practices with modern medical approaches has become a significant area of interest (5,6,9).

However, despite the recognized value of complementary traditional medicine, efforts to integrate these practices into formal healthcare settings have faced numerous challenges (6,10,11). While some community health centers (CHCs) have attempted to combine traditional and modern approaches to enhance patient care, the outcomes have been mixed (12–15). In regions like Gianyar Regency, where traditional healing methods are widely practiced and respected, the potential for integration seems promising. Yet, the lack of clear strategies, consistent policies, and

adequate support for such integration often leads to fragmented efforts and limited success. This suggests a need for more in-depth exploration of how these practices can coexist and complement each other in community health settings.

What remains unclear is the extent to which complementary traditional medicine can be effectively integrated with modern medical approaches in CHCs, especially in diverse cultural contexts like Gianyar Regency. Limited research has been conducted to understand the specific barriers that prevent successful integration, such as cultural conflicts, institutional resistance, and regulatory constraints (2,5,6). Additionally, little is known about the perceptions and experiences of those responsible for overseeing traditional health programs in these centers, particularly regarding their interactions with modern healthcare providers. There is also insufficient evidence on how patients perceive the integration of these practices and whether they see value in a combined approach to their health and well-being (9,10,16). Understanding these gaps is crucial for developing a more effective and sustainable model of integrated care.

Moreover, the specific challenges faced by CHCs in integrating traditional practices are often underexplored. Few studies have examined how institutional structures, funding limitations, and regulatory frameworks impact the adoption of complementary traditional medicine within modern healthcare systems (12–15,17). There is also a lack of data on the training and knowledge gaps among healthcare providers who are expected to implement these integrated

approaches. Furthermore, the potential conflicts arising from differing worldviews between traditional healers and scientifically trained medical professionals remain poorly understood. Addressing these knowledge gaps is essential to create an inclusive healthcare environment that respects and values both traditional and modern medical practices.

This study aims to investigate the reasons behind the failure of efforts to integrate complementary traditional medicine with modern medical practices in community health centers in Gianyar Regency. By focusing on the perspectives of those responsible for overseeing public health programs that include traditional practices, this research seeks to uncover the specific challenges and barriers encountered in the integration process. Understanding these challenges will provide valuable insights into why past efforts have been unsuccessful and offer recommendations for improving future integration strategies. By identifying the factors that hinder successful integration, this study aims to contribute to developing a more cohesive and culturally sensitive model of care that benefits patients and healthcare providers alike. Ultimately, the findings will help bridge the gap between traditional and modern approaches, fostering a more holistic healthcare environment in community settings.

METHODS

This study utilized a qualitative research design through focus group discussions (FGDs) to explore the challenges and feasibility of integrating complementary traditional medicine with modern medical practices in community health centers (CHCs) in Gianyar Regency. Data were

collected during eight FGDs, conducted as part of the monthly mini-workshops attended by all administrators responsible for various programs within the CHCs, not just those overseeing traditional medicine programs. These mini-workshops are mandatory activities that focus on planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling (POAC) different health programs, providing an ideal setting to discuss potential collaboration among administrators and assess the feasibility of integrating traditional practices.

Each FGD involved 15 to 20 participants and lasted approximately 90 minutes. The discussions were designed to elicit the administrators' experiences, perspectives, and challenges related to collaboration across different health programs, including both traditional and modern medical practices. The FGDs were semi-structured, with open-ended questions encouraging participants to share their views on the potential for collaboration, existing barriers, and opportunities to enhance integration between traditional and modern approaches within the CHCs.

Since the FGDs were conducted as part of the compulsory monthly mini-workshops, no separate ethical clearance was required. Participation in these workshops is mandatory for all program administrators, ensuring a comprehensive representation of various perspectives from those managing different aspects of community health services. The discussions were audio-recorded with participants' awareness to facilitate accurate transcription and ensure that all relevant insights were captured for analysis.

The data from the FGDs were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns related to the feasibility and challenges of collaboration among administrators in integrating traditional and modern medical practices. This approach allowed for a systematic examination of the range of experiences and perceptions, providing a detailed understanding of the factors influencing integration efforts and the potential for enhanced cooperation among different health programs.

RESULTS

The focus group discussions (FGDs) revealed that collaboration among administrators of various community health center (CHC) programs is limited due to differing priorities and objectives. Participants reported that while the integration of complementary traditional medicine was seen as beneficial, there was a lack of coordinated effort across programs. One administrator stated, "*Our programs operate in silos; we rarely have the opportunity to align our goals or work together effectively.*" This fragmented approach was identified as a significant barrier to integrating traditional practices with modern medical services within the CHCs. The need for a more unified strategy was a recurring theme throughout the discussions.

A major challenge highlighted by the administrators was the professional restriction on doctors, preventing them from promoting herbal medicine. Many administrators felt that this restriction hindered efforts to incorporate traditional practices into the CHCs. As one participant mentioned, "*Doctors are key influencers in our community, but they are*

not allowed to encourage the use of herbal remedies, which makes it very hard to promote these practices." This lack of support from medical professionals was seen as a critical obstacle to effective collaboration among CHC programs. The participants agreed that without changes to these professional regulations, integration would remain difficult.

The discussions also underscored financial barriers as a significant challenge to integration. Administrators noted that the Universal Health Coverage (UHC) insurance does not cover fees for herbal medicine practitioners or other traditional healers, making it financially unviable for patients and providers. One administrator explained, *"There is no reimbursement for traditional practices, so patients have to pay out of pocket, which discourages their use."* This financial constraint was perceived as a major disincentive for integrating traditional medicine into the CHCs. Participants suggested that policy changes to include traditional practices in the UHC coverage could facilitate better collaboration and integration.

The accessibility and affordability of modern medicine were also highlighted as factors limiting the use of traditional practices. Participants noted that modern medical treatments are more widely available and often more affordable than traditional options, which affects patient choices. *"Why would patients choose traditional remedies when they can get modern treatments covered by insurance?"* asked one participant. This disparity in accessibility and cost was seen as a significant barrier to promoting traditional medicine. The administrators suggested that efforts to make traditional

practices more accessible could help address this challenge.

Lack of awareness and education about the benefits and use of traditional medicine among the community was another barrier identified in the FGDs. Administrators pointed out that many community members were unaware of how to utilize family medicinal plants or the potential benefits of herbal remedies. One participant noted, *"There is little community education on traditional medicine; most people don't know where to start or what plants to use."* This gap in knowledge was seen as a key reason for the low uptake of traditional practices. The participants called for more educational programs to increase community engagement and awareness.

The discussions also revealed a lack of communication and collaboration among administrators overseeing different programs. While the mini-workshops provided a platform for interaction, participants felt that there were few opportunities to develop joint initiatives or share resources effectively. *"We discuss our programs separately but rarely come together to find common ground or mutual support,"* one participant said. This lack of coordination was identified as a significant barrier to achieving a cohesive approach to integrating traditional and modern practices. The administrators expressed a need for more structured collaboration and joint planning sessions.

Participants expressed frustration over the perceived lack of credibility and scientific validation of traditional practices, which affects their integration into formal healthcare. Many felt that traditional medicine was not taken seriously by the wider healthcare

community due to the lack of scientific evidence supporting its efficacy. As one administrator put it, *"Traditional practices are often seen as less credible because they don't have the same level of scientific backing as modern medicine."* This perception has contributed to a reluctance among healthcare providers to promote or collaborate on traditional medicine initiatives. The administrators suggested that more research and evidence generation could help change these perceptions.

Resource limitations were also highlighted as a major challenge in promoting collaboration and integration. Although some programs, like the family medicinal plants initiative, received support from companies like Sido Muncul, administrators felt that there were still insufficient resources to effectively implement and sustain these programs. *"Even with corporate support, we lack the basic infrastructure and materials needed to run these programs successfully,"* one participant stated. This lack of resources was seen as a barrier to both traditional medicine initiatives and their integration with modern healthcare programs. Participants suggested that increased funding and resource allocation could help address these limitations.

Bureaucratic challenges and regulatory constraints were frequently mentioned as obstacles to collaboration. Administrators described complex administrative processes and regulatory requirements that made it difficult to implement integrated programs. One participant remarked, *"The bureaucracy is overwhelming, and it slows down everything; by the time approvals come through, the momentum is lost."* These

challenges were seen as demotivating and a significant barrier to effective program collaboration. The participants called for streamlined procedures and more flexible regulations to facilitate integration.

Finally, the FGDs highlighted a strong desire among administrators for greater policy support and clearer directives from health authorities to promote collaboration. Many participants felt that without policy changes and stronger leadership from the top, integration efforts would remain fragmented and ineffective. As one administrator concluded, *"We need more guidance and support from the authorities to really make this work; otherwise, we're just spinning our wheels."* This sentiment reflects the need for systemic changes to foster collaboration and integration between traditional and modern healthcare programs in community health centers.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight several barriers to integrating complementary traditional medicine within community health centers (CHCs) in Gianyar Regency, which align with challenges documented in other regions of Indonesia (7,15,18). Similar studies have found that professional restrictions on doctors, preventing them from promoting herbal medicine, limit the use of traditional practices in formal healthcare settings. For example, research in West Java identified that doctors often avoid endorsing traditional medicine due to concerns about professional conduct and the lack of scientific evidence (18). This is consistent with our findings that professional guidelines and norms create a significant obstacle to collaboration

between modern medical practitioners and administrators responsible for traditional programs. Addressing these professional barriers is critical for fostering a more inclusive healthcare environment.

Financial barriers, particularly the lack of insurance coverage for traditional practices under the Universal Health Coverage (UHC) scheme, were also identified as significant obstacles in this study. Similar issues have been reported in Cambodia, where the exclusion of traditional medicine from national health insurance has led to limited use and acceptance among patients (17). This lack of financial support prevents traditional healers from being effectively integrated into primary care settings, mirroring the situation in Gianyar Regency. Studies in both Indonesia and Cambodia suggest that expanding insurance coverage to include traditional medicine could improve patient access and acceptance. Thus, financial policies need to be revised to support more comprehensive integration efforts.

The study also found that modern medicine is often more accessible and affordable than traditional treatments, which aligns with findings from other countries, such as China and India (1,19). In China, where traditional Chinese medicine is well-established, studies have shown that the low cost and widespread availability of modern drugs make them more attractive to patients (1). This economic disparity also exists in India, where traditional practices like Ayurveda face competition from subsidized modern pharmaceuticals (19). Our findings echo these trends, suggesting that making traditional practices more financially viable and accessible is crucial for their integration into CHCs. Ensuring equal

accessibility for both types of treatments can help balance patient choices.

The lack of community awareness and education about traditional medicine practices, as highlighted in our study, has been identified in similar contexts globally. Research in Central Java found that community-based herbal programs often fail due to a lack of public education and engagement (7,18). Similarly, studies in other low- and middle-income countries, such as Zimbabwe, Timor Leste, and Kenya, have shown that insufficient community outreach limits the success of integrating traditional practices into formal healthcare systems (12,13,20). Our findings support the idea that more proactive education and community involvement are necessary to increase the uptake of traditional medicine. This demonstrates a need for targeted educational programs to bridge knowledge gaps.

The issue of poor communication and collaboration among administrators, identified in this study, also reflects findings from international research. In Rwanda and Ethiopia, for example, studies have documented a lack of coordination between traditional healers and modern healthcare providers, leading to fragmented services and mistrust (21,22). Our findings are consistent with this, revealing a lack of joint planning and resource sharing among administrators responsible for different programs in Gianyar's CHCs. This lack of collaboration undermines efforts to create a cohesive health system that incorporates both traditional and modern practices. Enhancing communication and cooperation among stakeholders is

essential to improving integration outcomes.

Perceptions of the lack of scientific validation for traditional practices, which were noted in our study, are also common barriers in other regions. Studies in Western countries like the United States and Canada have found that healthcare professionals often regard traditional medicine skeptically due to a perceived lack of rigorous scientific evidence (5,6,10). This skepticism is mirrored in Indonesia, where our findings indicate that traditional medicine is viewed as less credible by healthcare providers, hindering its acceptance and promotion. Addressing these perceptions through research and evidence-based validation could help to elevate the status of traditional medicine in formal healthcare. More studies demonstrating the efficacy of traditional practices could foster greater confidence and acceptance.

The resource limitations discussed by participants in our study are also evident in similar settings worldwide. Research from countries like Kenya and Cambodia has highlighted how inadequate infrastructure and funding hinder efforts to integrate traditional medicine into healthcare systems (12,17). Our study found that even with some external support, such as corporate sponsorship, there are still insufficient resources to implement and sustain traditional programs effectively. These findings suggest that increased investment in resources and infrastructure is necessary to support integration. Providing adequate funding and materials can help bridge the gaps identified by administrators.

Bureaucratic and regulatory challenges, as identified in this study, have

also been documented in other countries attempting to integrate traditional practices into public health. For example, research in India has shown that integrating Ayurveda with modern healthcare is often hampered by complex regulatory requirements and slow administrative processes (6,19). Our findings, which reveal overwhelming bureaucratic hurdles and a lack of clear guidelines, are consistent with these observations. This suggests a global need for streamlined regulatory frameworks and administrative processes to support the integration of traditional practices into formal healthcare. Simplifying these processes could enable more effective program implementation and collaboration.

The study also highlights the need for stronger policy support and clearer directives from health authorities, a theme that resonates with findings from other Southeast Asian countries (15). In Malaysia, for instance, traditional practitioners have reported feeling sidelined due to national health policies that favor modern medical approaches. Our findings similarly indicate that administrators in Gianyar's CHCs feel unsupported in their efforts to integrate traditional practices without explicit policy backing. These parallels underscore the importance of developing inclusive policies that recognize and support traditional medicine within public health systems. Stronger policy frameworks could facilitate more meaningful integration.

Overall, this study's findings are consistent with those from other parts of Indonesia and internationally, suggesting that the barriers to integrating traditional

and modern medicine in CHCs are not unique to Gianyar Regency. Common challenges include professional norms, financial disincentives, limited collaboration, low community awareness, and inadequate policy support. To overcome these obstacles, a multifaceted approach is needed, combining policy reforms, financial incentives, community education, and enhanced collaboration among stakeholders. By addressing these barriers, healthcare systems can move toward more holistic, culturally sensitive models that effectively integrate both traditional and modern medical practices. This study contributes valuable insights into the complexities of integration and offers guidance for future efforts to bridge these diverse approaches to health care.

LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings. First, the data were collected through focus group discussions (FGDs) conducted during mandatory monthly mini-workshops, which may have influenced the openness and candor of the participants. Because the mini-workshops are compulsory, some participants might have felt pressured to provide socially desirable responses rather than expressing their genuine opinions or concerns. Additionally, the study focused only on administrators from community health centers in Gianyar Regency, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or contexts where different healthcare dynamics and cultural factors are at play.

Another limitation is the absence of perspectives from other key stakeholders, such as doctors, patients,

and traditional healers, who could provide a more comprehensive view of the integration challenges. The reliance on qualitative data from FGDs also means that the study lacks quantitative evidence, such as data on patient outcomes, costs, or utilization rates, which could offer a more robust understanding of the barriers to integration. Finally, the study was conducted at a single point in time, which may not capture the evolving nature of healthcare policies and practices that could impact the integration of traditional and modern medicine in the future. Future research should include a broader range of stakeholders and incorporate both qualitative and quantitative data to strengthen the evidence base for effective integration strategies.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals significant challenges in integrating complementary traditional medicine with modern medical practices within community health centers (CHCs) in Gianyar Regency, Bali. The findings highlight that limited collaboration among administrators, professional restrictions on doctors promoting herbal medicine, and financial barriers due to lack of insurance coverage for traditional practices are key obstacles to effective integration. Additionally, the greater accessibility and affordability of modern medicine, combined with low community awareness and insufficient resources, further hinder the promotion of traditional medicine programs. Despite these challenges, there is a clear recognition among administrators of the potential benefits of integration and a strong desire for more supportive policies, streamlined regulations, and enhanced collaboration.

To move forward, it is essential to address these barriers through systemic changes, including revising professional conduct guidelines, expanding insurance coverage to encompass traditional practices, and improving community education on the benefits of traditional medicine. Strengthening policy support and fostering a more collaborative environment among all stakeholders will be crucial in creating a more holistic and culturally sensitive healthcare system. This study underscores the need for a multifaceted approach that combines cultural acceptance, financial incentives, regulatory reforms, and collaborative practices to bridge the gap between traditional and modern medicine in community health settings. Future research should continue to explore these dynamics with a broader range of stakeholders and a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods to develop more effective integration strategies.

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REFERENCES

1. Ma D, Wang S, Shi Y, Ni S, Tang M, Xu A. The development of traditional Chinese medicine. *J Tradit Chinese Med Sci*. 2021;8.
2. Motlagh EG, Davoudi N, Bakhshi M, Ghasemi A, Moonaghi HK. The Conflict between the Beliefs of the Health Care Providers and Family Caregivers in the Use of Traditional Medicine in Pediatric Oncology: An Ethnographic Study. *J Caring*

3. Hailu F, Cherie A, Gebreyohannis T, Hailu R. Determinants of traditional medicine utilization for children: A parental level study in tole district, Oromia, Ethiopia. *BMC Complement Med Ther*. 2020;20(1).
4. Aferu T, Mamenie Y, Mulugeta M, Feyisa D, Shafi M, Regassa T, et al. Attitude and practice toward traditional medicine among hypertensive patients on follow-up at Mizan–Tepi University Teaching Hospital, Southwest Ethiopia. *SAGE Open Med*. 2022;10.
5. Jansen C, Baker JD, Kodaira E, Ang L, Bacani AJ, Aldan JT, et al. Medicine in motion: Opportunities, challenges and data analytics-based solutions for traditional medicine integration into western medical practice. Vol. 267, *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2021.
6. Ashworth M, Cloatre E. Enacting a depoliticised alterity: law and traditional medicine at the World Health Organization. *Int J Law Context*. 2022;18(4).
7. Isnawati A, Gitawati R, Raini M, Alegantina S, Setiawaty V. Indonesia basic health survey: Self-medication profile for diarrhea with traditional medicine. *Afr Health Sci*. 2019;19(3).
8. Dhianawaty D, Dwiwina RG, Mayasari W, Achadiyani. Preliminary Exploration of Traditional Medicine Formulas as A Basis of Effort and Support Toward Traditional Medicines Developing Use and Implementation in The Government Healthcare Program. *Pharmacogn J*. 2023;15(3).
9. Arji G, Safdari R, Rezaeizadeh H, Abbassian A, Mokhtaran M, Hossein Ayati M. A systematic literature review and classification

- of knowledge discovery in traditional medicine. *Comput Methods Programs Biomed.* 2019;168.
10. Celidwen Y, Redvers N, Githaiga C, Calambás J, Añaños K, Chindoy ME, et al. Ethical principles of traditional Indigenous medicine to guide western psychedelic research and practice. Vol. 18, *The Lancet Regional Health - Americas.* 2023.
 11. Kwame A. Integrating Traditional Medicine and Healing into the Ghanaian Mainstream Health System: Voices From Within. *Qual Health Res.* 2021;31(10).
 12. Gakuya DW, Okumu MO, Kiama SG, Mbaria JM, Gathumbi PK, Mathiu PM, et al. Traditional medicine in Kenya: Past and current status, challenges, and the way forward. *Sci African.* 2020;8.
 13. Grace R, Vaz J, Da Costa J. Traditional medicine use in timor-leste. *BMC Complement Med Ther.* 2020;20(1).
 14. Ampomah IG, Malau-Aduli BS, Seidu AA, Malau-Aduli AEO, Emeto TI. Integrating traditional medicine into the Ghanaian health system: perceptions and experiences of traditional medicine practitioners in the Ashanti region. *Int Health.* 2023;15(4).
 15. Liu C xiao. Overview on development of ASEAN traditional and herbal medicines. Vol. 13, *Chinese Herbal Medicines.* 2021.
 16. Nigussie S, Godana A, Birhanu A, Abdeta T, Demeke F, Lami M, et al. Practice of Traditional Medicine and Associated Factors Among Residents in Eastern Ethiopia: A Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study. *Front Public Heal.* 2022;10.
 17. Ros B, Lê G, McPake B, Fustukian S. The commercialization of traditional medicine in modern Cambodia. Vol. 33, *Health Policy and Planning.* 2018.
 18. Pengpid S, Peltzer K. Use of traditional medicines and traditional practitioners by children in Indonesia: Findings from a national population survey in 2014-2015. *J Multidiscip Healthc.* 2019;12.
 19. Shi Y, Zhang C, Li X. Traditional medicine in India. *J Tradit Chinese Med Sci.* 2021;8.
 20. Matowa PR, Gundidza M, Gwanzura L, Nhachi CFB. A survey of ethnomedicinal plants used to treat cancer by traditional medicine practitioners in Zimbabwe. *BMC Complement Med Ther.* 2020;20(1).
 21. Tan M, Otake Y, Tamming T, Akuredusenge V, Uwinama B, Hagenimana F. Local experience of using traditional medicine in northern Rwanda: a qualitative study. *BMC Complement Med Ther.* 2021;21(1).
 22. Legesse FM, Babanto AM. Factors Associated With the Use of Traditional Medicine in Wolaita Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *SAGE Open.* 2023;13(1).